

Evaluating Backflush Accounting's Impact on Financial Performance: A Study of Total Nigeria Plc in the Oil and Gas Sector

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ABSTRACT

This paper evaluated the impact of backflush accounting on the financial performance of oil and gas companies in Nigeria, specifically focusing on Total Nigeria Plc over a ten-year period from 2013 to 2022. Data were sourced from the annual reports of the company, with backflush accounting represented by proxies labour costs, raw material consumable costs, and inventory turnover costs, while financial performance was measured using return on assets (ROA). The study utilized an ex-post facto research design and employed descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis using e-View version 10. The findings revealed that labour costs, raw material consumable costs, and inventory turnover costs did not have a significant impact on the ROA of Nigerian oil and gas companies. The study concluded that backflush accounting does not significantly influence the financial performance of Total Nigeria Plc. It is recommended that Nigerian oil and gas companies should enhance their adoption of backflush accounting techniques to improve innovation, reduce unnecessary operational costs, lower inventory expenses, and maintain the flexibility needed to adapt to changing conditions, thereby potentially enhancing their financial performance.

Keywords: *Backflush Accounting, inventory turnover cost, raw material consumable, staff cost, return on assets*

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the oil sector is regarded as the most strategically important of all the industries. In international politics, oil is both a visible weapon and a significant source of income. Since oil was discovered in Nigeria in 1956, the sector has functioned as a "enclave" economy, making minimal economic contributions to the country. A few examples of prior attempts to implement the local content policy are the Petroleum Act's requirement that petroleum companies hire and educate Nigerians, the provisions pertaining to various treaties involving International Oil Companies ("IOCs") demanding technological transfer, the use of indigenous materials, and the hiring and advancement of Nigerians (Olugbenga, et al, 2022). Therefore, it is imperative that this true asset be properly documented in order to allow the government and oil firms to reap the greatest possible benefits from the natural endowment.

The field of accounting for oil and gas prospecting has evolved throughout time, but as of yet, no universally accepted standard exists for accounting for these

activities, despite the fact that many different corporations utilise widely accepted methodologies according to their own preferences. According to Pankaj and Nikul (2019), an effective accounting system can improve a company's performance because accounting is the foundation of business.

Backflush accounting is a costing method that adds cost to a process's output and is connected to the Just in Time (JIT) production system (Amahalu, et al., 2017). This cost accounting method divides costs between cost of products sold and inventory by concentrating on an organization's production and moving backward (Adeniyi, 2014). The goal of backflush accounting is to do away with the need for specific accounting transactions in a cost accounting setting (Ezelibe, et al., 2019). Instead of tracking the flow of materials through the manufacturing process, it concentrates on the organization's output and then works backwards in terms of cost allocation. To put it briefly, it's an accounting technique that doesn't record production costs until after a good or service is created, finished, or sold (Liberto, 2022). The article's components of backflush are labour costs, raw material consumable costs, and inventory turnover costs.

Labour costs, often referred to as staff costs, are the expenses incurred by workers who work for a company on a full- or part-time basis. Apart from the employer's share of the national social security and all other fringe benefit costs, it comprises gross earnings, salaries, commissions, and other compensation (Shambare, 2023). The quantity of resources used or given up for labour also had a role in the production of the particular commodities or services. It is merely the monetary appraisal of labour invested in creating commodities or services, according to Olayinka (2019). Employee expenses arise from both carrying out the task and providing field support (Abbas & Abu, 2019).

Raw materials that are used or consumed within a manufacturing cycle or any other specified period of time are referred to as consumable raw materials. These are material things that go into making the product. In order to create an item or provide a service, they indicate the cost of the components required (Onuora & Kenechukwu, 2019). The raw material consumable excludes all secondary materials, such as cleaning supplies required for manufacturing. They include all expenses directly related to the creation of a good or service, such as those incurred throughout the manufacturing process (Effiong & Oti, 2012).

Inventory turnover is the time interval between the day an item is purchased by an organisation and its sale. A complete inventory turnover occurs when the company sells all of its purchased stock, less any items lost to shrinkage or damage (Jenkins, 2022). It is determined as the percentage of times inventory is turned over in a particular year and can be defined as cost of goods sold divided by average inventory (Amahalu et al, 2017). Inventory represents the most significant single asset investment for the majority of producers, distributors, and retailers. Any unused resource kept for potential use is what it is defined as (Amahalu & Ezechukwu, 2017).

Ibrahim et al. (2017) describe financial performance as a company's ability to operate efficiently, economically, persist, grow, and adapt to both positive and negative factors in the external environment. Profitability is limited to the gains and losses incurred by the business. It is the abilities of the company to generate the intended financial consequences as contrasted to its predicted output (Mutende, et al.,

2017). The main objective of assessing financial performance is to ascertain the operational and financial aspects as well as the efficiency and performance of economic unity management, as demonstrated in financial records and reports (Ezejiofor & Erhirhie, 2018). Financial performance metrics like return on assets (ROA) are used to evaluate the study's finances.

Businesses evaluate their profitability using return on assets (ROA), a conventional financial indicator or accounting ratio. The profitability of an organisation is gauged by its return on assets (ROA). It shows how managers allocate the company's resources profitably (Irom, et al., 2018). This ratio assesses the total assets of the business in comparison to its revenue. This ratio evaluates the company's ability to make money out of its assets (Kabiru & Aliyu, 2019). A greater ROA ratio, according to Wen (2010), is a sign of a company's efficiency in using its own resources. With an emphasis on Total Nigeria Plc, the paper evaluates the backflush accounting and financial performance of Nigerian oil and gas companies.

Statement of the problem

Traditional cost accounting methods have been criticized for causing a "relevance loss" in accounting information, leading to the development of innovative approaches like backflush accounting. Despite this, many businesses still struggle to manage modern costing systems due to various challenges, such as the lengthy calculations required, delays in tracking expenses, a lack of awareness about technological advancements, inefficient staff cost structures, and limited understanding of the benefits of contemporary costing techniques, including backflush accounting.

As a result, there are often accounting inaccuracies or incomplete information about resource usage at different production stages when applying backflush costing. Furthermore, inconsistencies exist between this method and other accounting standards and widely accepted principles, making it difficult to provide necessary documentation for auditors. In light of these issues, this study aimed to examine the impact of backflush accounting techniques on the financial performance of the oil and gas sector in Nigeria, with a specific focus on Total Nigeria Plc.

Objectives of the study

The primary objective of the study is to evaluate the impact of backflush accounting on the financial performance of the oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study's particular goals include the following:

- i. Analyse how labour costs affect return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria.
- ii. Examine how the raw material consumable costs affect return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria.
- iii. Ascertain how inventory turnover costs affect return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria.

Research questions

The following research questions have been developed with the study's goal in mind.

- i. To what extent do labour costs affect return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria?
- ii. What effect do consumable raw material costs have on return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria?
- iii. How do inventory turnover costs affect return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

To analyze the data, the following null hypotheses formulated to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** Labour costs have no significant impact on returns on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** Raw material consumable costs have no significant impact on return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** Inventory turnover costs have no significant impact on return on assets of oil and gas Company in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

The present study employed backflush accounting as an independent variable to represent inventory turnover costs, raw material consumable costs, and labour costs. The dependent variable, financial performance, was defined as the firm's return on assets. Their links are as follows:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of Researchers, 2024

Concept of backflush accounting

The words backflush accounting and backflush costing are synonymous. This cost accounting approach, which starts with the company's production and works backward, splits costs between cost of products sold and inventory (Adeniyi, 2014). When combined with Just-In-Time production systems, back-flush costing introduces additional costs into the output process. Backflush accounting is defined as a method of bookkeeping that focusses mainly on an organization's manufacturing, with activities subsequently returning to inventory and cost of sales based on cost characteristics (CIMA, 1991). The conventional accounting system employs consecutive tracking, or accounting procedures that correspond to the actual order of manufacturing and purchase. The reason for the delayed term's formation is because backflush accounting postpones the costing of inventories to sales time and, ultimately, the accounting system's cost of returns. The work-in-progress account does not need to be kept separate since the introduction of backflush accounting (Omah & Okolie, 2013).

The goal of backflush accounting is to do away with the kind of in-depth accounting that is done in a cost accounting setting. It focuses on what the company produces and then proceeds backward in the allocation of expenses, rather than tracking the resources as they go through the production process. For businesses attempting to maintain the lowest possible level of inventory, it is suitable. It doesn't keep track of work-in-process (WIP) accounting separately. A variation of

back-flush accounting involves keeping a single raw material and work-in-progress account, often known as the raw and in-process account (RIP) or raw material account (Adeniyi, 2014).

Back-flush costing is a simplified process for allocating expenses between inventory and cost of sales. Assuming that they are a reasonable representation of the actual costs paid for, back-flushed costs are linked to the output produced, such as completed goods inventories and cost of sales, rather than reflecting the movement of products by means of the production procedure, according to the Chartered Institute of Management Accountants (2014). Backflush costing is a response to production's advancements and innovations. The just-in-time production environment's requirements led to the development of the backflush accounting method. The key distinction between backflush accounting and other accounting methods is the absence of a continuous tracking mechanism.

Frequently referred to as delayed or post-deduct costing, backflush costing is among the most basic techniques for cost accumulation employed by businesses that have implemented the Just-in-time (JIT) system. On the other hand, the JIT has a more comprehensive concept that emphasises continuous simplification and the elimination of waste and loss at every stage of the organization's operations. One of the objectives of this approach is to have zero ending inventories. It is more than just a method or methods to rack up expenses. According to Amahalu et al. (2017), backflush costing is a novel costing methodology designed to meet the needs of the Just-in-time (JIT) production system.

Labour costs

Companies pay their employees to improve their reputation in the community in an effort to maintain their favourable status as a business. government assistance social insurance, contributions from employers towards staff pension and insurance schemes, and employer payment made on their behalf that aren't reflected in the regular salary payments provided directly to employees are examples of additional compensation for employees. These payments are considered compensation since they are done for the benefit of the employees and because their labour usually determines the value of the

contributions, in one way or another (Ndum & Oranefo, 2021).

Labour costs are those related to the labour that is used throughout the manufacturing processes. Consequently, the amount of resources used or given up for labour in order to provide a given commodity or service is known as the staff cost. According to Olayinka (2019), it's only the monetary value assigned to the labour used to produce commodities or services. There are fixed and variable components to staff costs. Variable costs are directly correlated with the degree of activity, whereas fixed costs are constant with respect to a specific output level. It is also possible to divide staff costs into direct and indirect costs. Direct labour costs are correlated with the number of goods or services produced, in contrast to indirect labour costs, which are not. The cost of direct labour employees' salaries and benefits, as well as the cost of temporary assistance provided to workers who directly handle the manufacturer's products, make up the direct staff cost. To a noteworthy degree, direct staff expenses are easily managed and controlled, in contrast to indirect staff costs, which most manufacturing organisations struggle to control (Nworie & Nwoye, 2023).

Surbhi (2015) argues that a salary is a predetermined sum provided to staff members on a monthly or quarterly schedule depending on their work ethic and efficiency, whereas a wage is an hourly payment given to labourers based on the quantity of work they accomplish in a day. "People who are paid are known to as having blue collar labour jobs," he went on. This implies that these individuals are paid on a daily basis for low- or semi-skilled labour. Conversely, those who get compensation are frequently referred to as having "white collar office jobs," which denote that these people are highly skilled and trained, employed by an organisation, and enjoy an enviable position in the community at large.

Raw materials consumables costs

The primary component needed for the production of commodities or products is material. These materials can be broadly classified into two groups (Michael et al., 2012), direct materials and indirect materials. According to Effiong and Oti (2012), other names for direct materials include grocery stores, raw materials,

productive materials, raw stock, and simply materials without a label.

Various factors can lead to material waste, including leaks, damage, contamination, improper storage, subpar craftsmanship, low quality, theft, and obsolescence. According to Onuora and Kenechukwu (2019), all of these represent an increase in material prices and can be managed by effective control and efficient working practices. "Material cost" is the price of the materials needed to make a product or render a service. Indirect materials are not included in the cost of the materials including cleaning agents utilised for production. The price of the necessary materials required to create goods or services is the subject of these interchangeable terms, which are also known as direct material costs and raw material prices. Material costs are not the same as labour or administrative costs associated with production.

Direct material costs are a component of inventory costs and cost of sales in a manufacturing organisation. The amount recorded as direct material cost and the amount recorded as overhead or expense vary depending on how different organisations interpret this word. Direct material costs are instantly observable and directly tied to the production unit. Glass, for example, is a direct material cost in the flashlight manufacturing process (Lanen, et al, 2008).

Inventory turnover costs

One essential component of a business's current assets is inventory. The usual inventory of industrial firms consists of finished goods, raw materials, or work-in-progress. In general, To optimise working capital, it's important to find a balance between keeping as little inventory as feasible and having inventory for sales (Sunusi, et al., 2020). A substantial portion of a business's total assets are comprised of inventory. According to Yasin et al. (2013), it makes up 50% of the current assets and 35% of the total assets of retail company concerns.

Inventory turnover is calculated by dividing the cost of sold items by the average inventory, which indicates how rapidly things may be sold. The cost of inventory and the cost of goods sold are compared in inventory turnover. When the bulk of the items produced by the firm are sold, a high inventory turnover rate indicates that there is little remaining inventory (Imhanzenobe, 2019). One way to assess a

company's marketing effectiveness is through inventory turnover. Nonetheless, it might not be a smart idea to have a large inventory. Nonetheless, businesses with substantially or perfectly inelastic products have a tendency to store inventory during inflationary times in order to offer it at a higher price later on. However, maintaining inventory can be detrimental in a market where prices are generally stable due to its associated costs (holding cost and time value of money). Maintaining inventory delays revenue from products sold without payment.

The frequency at which a business sells and replenishes its inventory is measured by its inventory turnover. It is the proportion of the most recent inventory to the annual cost of sales. Another way to look at the ratio is the length of time that inventory is held (Amahalu et al., 2017). 365 days a year divided by 26 = 14 days for an average inventory holding duration, so an inventory turnover ratio of 26 means, for example, that inventory is kept for an average of two weeks. This ratio is best used to compare businesses within an industry because it varies greatly between industries (high turnover is a favourable indicator). This statistic illustrates how frequently a business sells off and refills its inventory during a certain time period. It is calculated by dividing the average inventory level by the cost of items sold. A comparatively low inventory turnover could be a sign of outdated inventory being carried to prevent deducting inventory losses from income or of poor inventory management, which involves carrying an excessive amount of inventory. In general, a high inventory turnover is preferred.

An efficiency measure called the inventory turnover ratio is used to evaluate how well supplies are kept on hand. The inventory turnover ratio is a metric used to evaluate an organization's effectiveness in managing its inventory (Corporate Finance Institute, 2023). It displays the number of times inventory is sold in a given year. Inventory management requires careful attention from management since it entails several risks, from the procurement of raw materials to the manufacture of finished goods. (Farooq, 2019). It is important to have a large proportion since it reduces holding costs related to storing and other holding charges. Comparing the ratios of businesses in the same industry is crucial, not those of businesses in other industries.

The average inventory is calculated by dividing the total inventory at the start and end of the year by two (Abdillah, 2020). The inventory turnover ratio, which shows how frequently inventory is "turned," or sold, during a certain time period, is calculated by dividing the cost of items sold by the total or average inventory. Using the ratio, one may ascertain whether inventory levels are out of proportion to sales.

Financial performance

Performance is important to every organisation. It is the actual performance of a given work judged against defined standards of preciseness, comprehensiveness, cost/efficiency, and rapidity as well as efficacy (Obi-Anike, et al, 2017). Performance measurements come in two flavours: financial and organisational. According to Jayiddin et al. (2017), the managerial strategy used by certain companies to increase an organization's productivity is known as organisational performance. The definition of financial performance is maximising shareholder advantages and profit on assets.

A company's ability to maximise its resource utilisation in order to generate profits is measured by its financial performance. It evaluates the profitability of an organisation. The amount of money earned above the costs incurred during the course of manufacturing within a specific time period is known as profit. According to Nworie and Ofoje (2022) it pertains to the excess of income over net operational costs.

According to Omari's (2020) statement, financial performance refers to a company's capacity to produce a respectable return on invested capital that satisfies shareholders and encourages new investors to make investments. Reluctantly, investors are always curious about the company's capacity to make the required earnings by making the best use of its limited resources. Since a profit is not produced when operating expenses are not yet covered, return is determined by evaluating earnings in relation to the amount and sources of financing (Kajola, et al., 2020).

Furthermore, Ibrahim and Hamid (2019) noted that a company's earnings, profitability, and value growth are measured by its financial performance, which is demonstrated by an increase in stock price and the accomplishment of its financial objectives. It assesses

how well and efficiently current assets, plant, and equipment are converted into profits (Nworie & Mba, 2022). According to Wuave et al. (2020), financial success can be assessed using the following metrics: net profit margin (NMP), profit after tax (PAT), return on equity (ROE), gross profit margin (ROA), and profit on assets (ROA). Return on Assets (ROA) is the study's financial performance metric.

Return on assets (ROA)

Return on assets, often known as "return on total assets," offers a thorough examination of profitability. This financial indicator evaluates a business's ability to generate revenue from all of its available resources (Yonas & Suharto, 2021). A statistic called return on assets (ROA) is used to evaluate how profitable a business is in comparison to its total assets. ROA provides insight into how well management uses its resources to turn a profit. Divide the company's annual revenue by the total value of its assets to get ROA.

By making comparisons net profit to the average of all assets over a certain time period, the ROA ratio, a measure of profitability, determines the net income generated by all assets. Return on assets, or ROA, measures a company's ability to generate revenue from its current assets. According to Amahalu et al. (2017), a high ROA denotes a smoothly running and efficiently performing organisation, while a low ROA may be a sign of inadequate management.

According to Obutor (2022), the management will be especially focused on the ROA figure at the end of the year. An organisation is making the most of its current asset base if its return on assets (ROA) is high. The ROA may show the value of further investment and the company's capacity to use it efficiently when paired with the return on investment statistic. For a corporation to run efficiently, it is imperative to analyse a low return on assets. A consistently low ROA may be a sign that management is not using the company's assets to their full potential or that the assets are no longer valuable.

Theoretical Framework

Traditional cost theory

Koutsoyiannis (1988) introduced traditional cost theory, which makes a distinction between short- and long-term expenses. The short term refers to the time frame in which some characteristics remain constant;

capital equipment and entrepreneurship are typically regarded as fixed in the short term. The length of time that all factors become changeable is known as the long run. Total costs are divided into two categories under the company's conventional concept: total fixed costs and total variable costs. Using the traditional idea of cost, an organisation may determine the quantity of production that results in the most profit at the lowest cost. The conventional theory of costs asserts that the law of variable proportions is reflected in the U-shaped short-run cost curves (AVC, ATC, and MC). With a fixed plant, there are two short-term phases: one during which the variable factor(s)'s productivity increases while unit costs fall, and the other during which the productivity decreases while unit costs rise.

Theory of Constraints (TOC)

Eliyahu M. Goldratt originally put forward the theory of constraints (TOC) in his 1984. According to the theory of constraints (TOC), a relatively small number of constraints restrict a controlled system's capacity to accomplish its objectives. There will undoubtedly be limitations. In order to identify which is the one and reorganise the rest of the business to make room for it, TOC uses a focussing process. The adage "a chain is no stronger than its weakest link" is appropriated by TOC from another source. This implies that weakest individuals or components have the potential to destroy processes, organisations, etc., or at the very least have a negative impact on the result.

TOC fervently supports keeping all capacity expenses out of products. Three essential considerations are inventory, operating expenses, and throughput. TOC calculates profit as throughput minus operating costs. The difference between revenues and raw material costs is also measured by throughput. Capacity cost should be utilised in the TOC to generate value for the client. Low or nonexistent profitability may result from poor utilisation of capacity in various business processes if all firm resources are not aligned with the throughput the company creates. In other words, TOC can aim for increased value in its profit. A goal can be identified by using the Theory of Constraints (TOC) process, which involves first determining the primary constraint preventing the objective from being achieved and then methodically removing it.

This study is anchored on Eliyahu Goldratt's Theory of Constraints, developed in 1984. The theory emphasizes that complex systems, such as production processes, consist of multiple interconnected operations, with each operation potentially acting as a constraint on the entire system—essentially the "weakest link in the chain." One of the most compelling aspects of the Theory of Constraints is its natural prioritization of improvement efforts, with the current constraint always taking precedence. Resulting in a situation when instant changes are required, TOC offers a very targeted method for accomplishing quick gains.

Empirical Review

Labour costs and return on assets

Mirko et al. (2011) evaluated how minimum wages affected business profitability by taking advantage of the adjustments brought about by the 1999 implementation of a national minimum wage in the United Kingdom. The study applies a difference-in-differences method using pre-policy data on wage distribution. It was discovered that while minimum wages increase pay, they also dramatically lower profitability (particularly in sectors of the economy with strong market positions). This aligns with a basic model that shows how increases in minimum wages translate into decreases in profits. A longer-term adjustment to the minimum wage through declines in net entry rates appears to be supported by some research.

Hameed et al. (2014) assessed the effect of pay on worker performance using real data from Pakistan's banking industry. They created a survey. SPSS 17.0 was used to conduct regression and correlation analyses on the gathered data. The results indicate that compensation has a beneficial effect on employee performance. The correlation analysis shows that each of the independent variables has a weak to slightly favorable relationship with the others. Every independent variable has a somewhat beneficial effect on employee performance, according to regression analysis.

Ojeleye (2017) looked on the connection between output and compensation. A standardized questionnaire was distributed to 83 workers of the Abdul Gusau Polytechnic and State College of Education in Zamfara State in order to collect information on pay and performance. Multiple

regression models and Pearson correlation were used to analyze the data using SPSS 22.0 and E-views 9.0. The results demonstrated that pay and performance are strongly and favorably correlated, and that bonuses, wages, and other forms of incentives motivate employees.

Nwarogu and Iormbagah's (2018) study looked at how indirect costs affected the profitability of listed brewing companies in Nigeria from 2010 to 2015. The study used an ex-post factor research technique and used regression analysis to analyze secondary data. The results show a strong relationship between profitability, administrative costs, labour salaries and wages, and rent costs. The findings indicated that while salaries and wages had no appreciable effect on the profitability of a business, administrative costs had a significant effect.

The effect of human resource costs on the financial statements of publicly traded Nigerian brewing companies between 2007 and 2019 was investigated by Ndum and Oranefo (2021). The Ex-Post-Facto research design was used in this investigation. These firms' publicly accessible annual reports and accounts provided the data for this study. According to the study's findings, personnel costs significantly increase the percentage of listed brewing businesses' net profit, but they also have a favorable and small influence on their return on assets.

An empirical assessment of the financial performance's sensitivity to the overhead costs of Nigerian deposit money banks was conducted by Eneh et al. in 2022. It lasted for twelve years, from 2009 to 2020. The results of the diagnostic tests showed that heteroskedasticity and unit roots were present. Panel least squares regression analysis was applied. The return on equity was negatively impacted by salary and wages as well as director remunerations, albeit very slightly. However, the natural logarithm of total assets and audit fees had a significant beneficial influence.

The costs of certain enterprises were the focus of a study on the drivers of operating profit carried out by Nworie and Nwoye (2023). According to the study, by examining certain areas of their spending, it is feasible to predict the trajectory of the profitability of publicly listed consumer products firms in Nigeria. An ex post facto research design is used in this study. The

ordinary least square regression approach, descriptive statistics, and correlation analysis were used to evaluate secondary data that was gathered between 2011 and 2020. The results demonstrated a strong relationship between labor costs and the operational profit ratios of publicly listed consumer firms in Nigeria.

Raw material consumable and return on assets

Rehana and Mahmuda (2011) analysed the use of back-flush accounting in their investigation of cost management techniques in Bangladeshi industrial companies. A total of seventy manufacturing organisations were surveyed in this survey. Only five cost management tools have an effect on profit planning decisions, according to the findings of multiple regression analysis, and only three satisfied cost management tools are significant in terms of overall cost management tool satisfaction. Additionally, there is a positive but marginally significant relationship between back-flush accounting and financial performance.

Amir and Mohammed (2014) explored back-flush costing and back-flush accounting in Iran utilising a quantitative approach to investigate the impact of back-flush accounting in Iranian corporations that manufacture goods. They discovered that the annual values of inventories are underestimated using back-flush costing. Second, it was shown that private businesses who employ activity-based costing or just-in-time manufacturing systems for inventory are more likely to adopt backflush costing. Backflush costing is not suitable for use in meeting external reporting obligations and is not compliant with GAAP.

On the other side, Mamidu and Akinola (2019) investigated how Nigerian manufacturing companies performed in relation to cost management. The ordinary least squares model was. The research revealed that the profits derived from manufacturing operations are considerably and adversely impacted by direct material cost, direct labour cost, and production overhead.

Ajala (2021) looked into how cost control affected the financial performance of pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria between 2010 and 2019. In our investigation, we employed secondary data. The study's factors included expenses for sales and distribution, salaries and wages, raw material costs, profit after taxes,

R&D, and training. Panel regression analysis was used to look at how cost containment affected the financial performance of pharmaceutical companies in Nigeria. The results demonstrated that cost control significantly affects Nigerian pharmaceutical companies' profitability.

Erasmus (2021) carried out an empirical study to investigate the relationship between the financial results of Nigerian listed deposit money banks from 2010 to 2018 and their cost management strategies. The inquiry employed a thorough triangulation research technique. The financial health of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks was shown to be significantly impacted by activity-based costing, target costing, and standard costing, according to research that used ordinary least square regression to evaluate the hypotheses.

Njeri (2021) assessed how cost control affected Kenyan agricultural businesses' performance using a descriptive panel study methodology. Multiple panel regression models were employed for collecting and analysing of secondary data spanning a ten-year period, from 2009 to 2018. The study's conclusions demonstrated that cost control significantly affects Kenyan agribusiness firms' return on investment.

Egwuatu (2021) investigated the connection between material management and organizational effectiveness in the South-East Nigerian brewery industry. A descriptive survey was the study design that was employed. The instrument used in the study was a questionnaire. Simple percentage analysis and multivariate regression analysis were also applied. Version 21 of SPSS was used. Results indicated that at Nigeria Brewer Industries South-East, material control significantly boosts organisational productivity. In South-East Nigerian breweries, material planning method significantly increases organisational productivity.

The goal of Niyi et al. (2022) was to evaluate how cost structure affected the financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing companies that were listed. The financial statements covering the years 2011 through 2020 were used for the analysis. Two methods were used: an ex post facto study approach and descriptive analysis with regression and correlation analysis. The Nigerian Exchange Group presents the study's findings, which support the notion

that an industrial enterprise's cost structure significantly affects its financial success.

Inventory turnover costs and return on assets

Amahalu et al. (2017) used information from the annual financial statements and reports of eleven (11) published food and beverage companies for the years 2010 to 2015 to investigate backflush accounting and the financial performance of listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. According to the study, at the 5% significant level, backflush accounting had a positive and statistically significant impact on the ROA, ROE, and EPS of food and beverage businesses listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

With the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20, Ezelibe et al. (2019) used both basic regression and descriptive statistics to examine the effects of back-flush accounting practices on the financial performance of certain reported manufacturers in Nigeria from 2012 to 2018. The results showed a significant and positive relationship between back-flush accounting and Nigerian manufacturing enterprises' return on assets.

Umar (2019) investigated the relationship between inventory turnover and a business's profitability. Seventy-nine businesses from Pakistan's cement, sugar, and auto industries make up the sample. Information from 2006 to 2015 is included in the data collection. Throughout the process, the Generalized Method of Moment (GMM) was used. The study's findings demonstrate that return on asset is unaffected by the inventory turnover ratio. According to the second model, the return on equity is unaffected by the log of sale (LOS), sales growth ratio, inventory turnover ratio, and networking capital (NWC). The final regression model shows that neither the inventory turnover ratio nor the net profitability margin ratio (LOS) have an effect.

Abdillah (2020) looked into how inventory turnover affected the profitability of automakers that were listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange between 2015 and 2017. This study used statistical analysis, more especially, basic linear regression analysis, together with a quantitative analytical technique to examine conventional hypotheses. The method used is called purposeful sampling, and each year a total of eighteen businesses are included in the sample. The results of

the research imply that inventory turnover has no beneficial effect on return on assets.

The impact of the inventory turnover period on the profitability of listed Nigerian conglomerate firms was examined by Sunusi et al. (2020). The data came from the annual reports of public companies for the years 2007 through 2016. It was discovered that the generalised least square (FGLS) regression approach offered a workable answer. The findings imply a negative correlation between listed Nigerian conglomerate enterprises' profitability and inventory turnover management.

Vidhyapriya, et al. (2020) statistically conducted research on economic evaluation of the inventory behaviour by investing the inventory turnover enterprises in India for the period 2011-2018. Panel data were used in the analysis. Inventory turnover is favourably correlated with capital expenditure and sales surprises and negatively correlated with gross margin, according to the predicted outcomes derived from log linear models.

Using data from a case study in the Polish food industry spanning from 2005 to 2017, Gołaś (2020) examined the impact of inventory control on profitability. This was accomplished at every level of the Polish food industry sub-sectors using the panel data approach. The study's conclusions show that a decrease in the days-in-stock ratio for both materials and finished goods causes a clear propensity for the daily volume of inventory sold to decrease overall stocks.

Gap in review of literature

The empirical research from prior studies which concludes in 2020 and is part of the study mentioned above is the most comparable. The study indicated that, during the most recent period (2013–2022), there has been minimal research done on the impact of backflush accounting on the financial performance of oil and gas corporations in Nigeria, with a specific focus on Total Nigeria Plc. This closes a gap in the literature, supporting the methodology used in the study and contributing a substantial quantity of fresh knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The research is an ex-post facto analysis that uses data that has already been gathered to offer a systematic and practical solution for investigating issues.

Sources of data

Secondary data documentation from Total Nigeria Plc's accounts and yearly reports covering the period from 2013 to 2022 were used.

Population of the study

Ten publicly traded firms engaged in oil marketing and production and listed on the NGX Group comprise the study's population. Arдова Plc, Conoil, Eterna, Japaul Gold and Venture, MRS Oil Nigeria, Total Nigeria, Oando, Seplat Energy, RAKUNITY Plc, and Capital Oil are a few of these businesses.

Sample method

The study used the census sampling technique. Because of its long-standing dominance in the market, Total Nigeria Plc was expressly selected as a study sample, ensuring data availability for the ten-year period (2013–2022).

Model specification

The equation has an explicit definition of:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LCO_{it} + \beta_2 TA_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad . \quad 1$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RMC_{it} + \beta_2 TA_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad . \quad 2$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ITC_{it} + \beta_2 TA_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad . \quad 3$$

General model:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LCO_{it} + \beta_2 RMC_{it} + \beta_3 ITC_{it} + \beta_4 TA_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad .4$$

Where: β_0 = intercept (Constant term).

β_1 = Coefficient of backflush accounting

μ_{it} = the error terms or variations that cannot be explained by the above model.

i = the number of firms and

t = the number of time periods.

ROA = Return on assets

LCO = Labour costs

RMC = Raw material consumable costs

ITC = Inventory turnover costs

TA = Total Asset

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = Regression coefficients.

Decision Rule: The alternative hypothesis is discarded and the null hypothesis is established if the p-value is smaller than or equal to 0.05, threshold of significance, and conversely.

Table 1: Description and Measurement of variables

S/n	Variable	Variable type	Measurement
1	Return on assets	Dependent	<u>Profit after tax</u> Total Asset
2	Labour costs	Independent variable	Salaries and wages
3	Raw material consumable	Independent variable	Material costs
4	Inventory turnover costs	Independent variable	<u>Cost of goods sold</u> Total Asset
5	Total Asset	Control variable	Measured by natural log of total assets

Source: Authors Compilation (2024).

Method of data analysis

Using e-view 10 statistical software, inferential statistics for the hypotheses were performed applying the coefficient of correlation, a powerful tool for assessing the trend and strength of a connection involving two variables. The study employed regression analysis using the Ordinary Least Square approach. Regression analysis describes the implications or effects of changes in the numerical values of the variables in question and predictions regarding the significance of a variable according to the values of the other factors.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

Table 2: Data showing variables for the study of Total Nigeria Plc

Year (s)	Return on assets (ROA)	Labour Costs (LCO)	Raw material consumable costs(RMC)	Inventory turnover costs (ITC)	Log of Total Assets (LTA)
2013	0.067176953	5,874,741	2,120,183	14,640,893	18.19005
2014	0.046315784	6,906,511	1,740,789	19,826,763	18.37477
2015	0.048378709	6,786,096	1,270,706	17,391,520	18.24219
2016	0.10806466	7,483,750	464,342	34,902,844	18.73497
2017	0.074265224	8,240,675	310,154	26,666,240	18.49747
2018	0.060072789	8,815,810	4,512,056	30,045,177	18.70225
2019	0.016753395	8,805,779	8,170,792	33,642,490	18.72839
2020	0.014367687	8,612,443	4,318,892	21,619,936	18.78263
2021	0.080784811	11,063,187	5,832,179	29,202,091	19.15655
2022	0.052363719	13,076,549	23,090,221	59,275,749	19.54501

Source: Authors Compilations 2024

Data Analysis

Table 3: Shows the descriptive statistics

	ROA	LCO	RMC	ITC	LTA
Mean	0.056854	15.93745	14.77358	17.09665	18.69543
Median	0.056218	15.94666	14.92276	17.14433	18.71532
Maximum	0.108065	16.38633	16.95492	17.89771	19.54501
Minimum	0.014368	15.58617	12.64482	16.49933	18.19005
Std. Dev.	0.028346	0.236155	1.312247	0.402906	0.414670
Skewness	0.058441	0.469620	-	0.403327	0.737725
			0.131662		
Kurtosis	2.518643	2.596364	2.273648	2.763365	2.863514
Jarque-Bera	0.102236	0.435455	0.248720	0.294452	0.914825
Probability	0.950167	0.804344	0.883062	0.863099	0.632919
Sum	0.568544	159.3745	147.7358	170.9665	186.9543
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.007231	0.501922	15.49792	1.460999	1.547557

Source: e-views output, 2024

Table 3 above displays the average values for Return on Assets (ROA), Labour costs (LCO), Raw material consumable costs (RMC), Inventory turnover costs (ITC), and Total Asset (TA) for Total Nigeria Plc over a ten-year period from 2013 to 2022. These values are approximately ₦0.056854, ₦15.93745, ₦14.77358, ₦17.09665, and ₦18.69543, respectively. It equally illustrates their varied minimum and maximum values as well as their variations over the years. On the other hand, a measure of departure from the mean is the sum of squares dev. above. The standard deviation value, which illustrates that the lesser the value, the smaller the variation of the collection from the mean, and the greater the significance, the wider the divergence of the series from the mean, was used to highlight the dispersion in the data series.

It is stated that a probability distribution that is totally symmetric around the mean will have zero skewness. As a result of the ROA, ITC, RMC, SCO, and LTA series' normality (0.058441, 0.403327, -0.131662, 0.469620, and 0.737725, respectively), it can be concluded that all of the series have a normal distribution. Additionally, the probability values of the Jarque-Berra statistics for all of the series 0.102236, 0.294452, 0.248720, 0.435455 and 0.914825 are greater than the acceptable 0.05, with the corresponding p-values 0.950167, 0.863099, 0.883062, 0.804344 and 0.632919 for ROA, ITC, RMC, SCO, and LTA being higher than 0.05. The converted series is used to estimate the regression model since it satisfies one of the conditions of

Ordinary Least Square Regression, which is the normality of the series.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Labour costs have no significant impact on returns on assets of oil and gas firm in Nigeria.

Table 4: Results of hypothesis one tested

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LCO	-1.56E-08	1.88E-08	-0.831223	0.4333
LTA	0.079781	0.096988	0.822584	0.4379
C	-1.300738	1.657914	-0.784563	0.4584
R-squared	0.090473	Mean dependent var		0.056854
Adjusted R-squared	-0.169391	S.D. dependent var		0.028346
S.E. of regression	0.030653	Akaike info criterion		-
				3.888850
Sum squared resid	0.006577	Schwarz criterion		-
				3.798075
Log likelihood	22.44425	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-
				3.988431
F-statistic	0.348155	Durbin-Watson stat		1.597565
Prob(F-statistic)	0.717553			

Source: E-views output, 2024

The hypothesis represents 9.05% of the variance in the dependent variable (return on assets), according to the coefficient of determination, or R-square. This indicates that 9.05% LCO accounts for the entire fluctuation in return on assets. The Adjusted R² is therefore -0.169391. This show that the independent variable (labour costs) given in the model can explain only roughly -1.69% of the fluctuations in the dependent variable.

The outcome of the ordinary least square regression analysis, which is displayed in the table above to assess the degree to which labour costs impact return on assets, reveals that -1.56 labour costs and a constant factor of -1.30 account for the return on assets; this is evident from the regression equation that was used to test the magnitude of impact that labour costs has on return on assets as illustrated below;

$$ROA = -1.30 - 1.56LCO + 0.08TA$$

This indicates that the return on assets will fluctuate by -1.56 for each unit change in labour costs. This suggests that personnel costs have a negative impact on return on assets and shows a negative link. The P-value from the coefficient table was used to evaluate how personnel expenses affected return on assets. Given that the p-value of 0.71 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, it may be concluded that labour costs have a negligible effect on the model. Therefore, we agree with the null

hypothesis, which claims that employee expenses have no discernible effect on the return on assets of Nigerian oil and gas enterprises.

H₀₂: Raw material consumable costs have no significant impact on return on assets of oil and gas company in Nigeria.

Table 5: Results of hypothesis two tested

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RMC	-3.50E-09	2.42E-09	-1.449619	0.1904
LTA	0.048744	0.039515	1.233553	0.2572
C	-0.836271	0.728573	-1.147821	0.2888
R-squared	0.231425	Mean dependent var		0.056854
Adjusted R-squared	0.011832	S.D. dependent var		0.028346
S.E. of regression	0.028178	Akaike info criterion		-
				4.057236
Sum squared resid	0.005558	Schwarz criterion		-
				3.966461
Log likelihood	23.28618	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-
				4.156817
F-statistic	1.053881	Durbin-Watson stat		1.276093
Prob(F-statistic)	0.398017			

Source: E-views output, 2024

Return on assets, the dependent variable, has a variance that the model can explain by 23.14%, as shown by the coefficient of determination (R-square) of 0.231425. This suggests that 23.14% RMC accounted for all of the volatility in return on assets. The Adjusted R² is thus 0.011832. This indicates that the independent variable (raw material consumable costs) included in the model can only account for around 1.18% of the fluctuations in the dependent variable.

The outcome of the ordinary least square regression analysis, which appears in the table, intends to measure the extent of significance associated with the effects of raw material consumable costs on return on assets, as demonstrated by the regression equation that was utilised to test the degree of effect that these costs have on return on assets. It was discovered that -3.50 of the costs associated with consumable raw materials and a constant factor of -0.83 define return on assets;

$$ROA = -0.83 - 3.50 RMC + 0.05TA$$

Accordingly, a change of one unit in the consumable costs of raw materials will result in a change of -3.50 in return on assets. This shows an adverse relationship and implies that return on assets is negatively

impacted by the cost of consumable raw materials. The model's consumable raw material costs are negligible because the p-value of 0.39 is higher than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, we agree with the null hypothesis, which states that the cost of consumable raw materials has no discernible effect on the return on assets of Nigerian oil and gas companies. The considerable influence of raw material consumable costs on return on assets was assessed using the P-value from the coefficient table.

H₀₃: Inventory turnover costs have no significant impact on return on assets of oil and Gas Company in Nigeria.

Table 6: Results of hypothesis three tested

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ITC	6.73E-10	1.71E-09	0.394281	0.7051
LTA	-0.016245	0.052430	-0.309843	0.7657
C	0.341223	0.937725	0.363884	0.7267
R-squared	0.022410	Mean dependent var		0.056854
Adjusted R-squared	-0.256902	S.D. dependent var		0.028346
S.E. of regression	0.031779	Akaike info criterion		-
				3.816684
Sum squared resid	0.007069	Schwarz criterion		-
				3.725908
Log likelihood	22.08342	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-
				3.916264
F-statistic	0.080231	Durbin-Watson stat		1.869923
Prob(F-statistic)	0.923739			

Source: E-views output, 2024

The model predicts 2.24% of the difference in the dependent variable (return on assets), according to the R-square, or the squared value of the correlation coefficients. This shows that the entire variance in return on assets may be accounted by the ITC of 2.24%. The Adjusted R² is consequently -0.256902. This shows that the independent variables included in the model can only explain around -25.7% of the changes in the dependent variable.

The outcome of the ordinary least square regression analysis, which is displayed in the table to assess the degree of significance of the impact of inventory turnover costs on return on assets, indicates that 6.73 percent of inventory turnover costs and 0.34 constant factor account for return on assets. This is also supported by the regression model that is used to examine the impact of inventory turnover costs on return on assets, which is displayed below;

$$ROA = 0.34 + 6.73 ITC - 0.02 TA$$

This indicates that there will be 6.73 variations in return on assets for every unit change in inventory turnover costs. This demonstrates a positive correlation and suggests that the cost of inventory turnover has a favourable effect on return on assets. The significance of the relationship between inventory turnover costs and return on assets was ascertained using the P-value found in the coefficient table. Inventory turnover costs have a negligible impact on the model since the p-value of 0.92 is higher than the 0.05 alpha value. Therefore, we agree with the null hypothesis, which claims that the return on assets of Nigerian oil and gas companies is not significantly impacted by inventory turnover costs.

H₀₄: Labour costs, raw material consumable costs, Inventory turnover costs have no significant impact on returns on assets of oil and gas company in Nigeria.

Table 7: Results of hypothesis four tested

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
ITC	2.39E-09	1.83E-09	1.305863	0.2484
RMC	-5.37E-09	3.15E-09	-1.707422	0.1484
LCO	-1.34E-09	1.94E-08	-0.069334	0.9474
LTS	0.016476	0.102370	0.160946	0.8784
C	-0.280412	1.748380	-0.160384	0.8789
R-squared	0.439363	Mean dependent var		0.056854
Adjusted R-squared	-0.009146	S.D. dependent var		0.028346
S.E. of regression	0.028475	Akaike info criterion		-
				3.972701
Sum squared resid	0.004054	Schwarz criterion		-
				3.821409
Log likelihood	24.86351	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-
				4.138669
F-statistic	0.979608	Durbin-Watson stat		1.393513
Prob(F-statistic)	0.493849			

Source: E-views output, 2024

The coefficient of determination, as shown in Table 7 above is 0.439363, indicating that 43.9% of the difference in the dependent variable, return on assets, is explained by the model. This suggests that LCO, RMC, and ITC are responsible for 43.9% of the variation in return on assets. Consequently, the Adjusted R² is -0.009146. This shows that the independent variables provided in the model are only

capable of accounting for approximately -0.09% of the fluctuation in the dependent variable.

The findings of an ordinary least square regression analysis that was done to ascertain the significance of the association between labour expenses, inventory turnover costs, consumable raw material costs, and return on assets are shown in the table. The results of a regression study examining the relationship between inventory turnover cost and return on assets show that -1.34, -5.37, and 2.39 of the independent variables account for the return on assets.

$$ROA_{it} = -0.28 -1.34 LCO -5.37 RMC + 2.39ITC + 0.02TA$$

This indicates that the relationship is unfavourable and demonstrates that labour costs and raw material consumable costs have an adverse effect on return on assets whereas inventory turnover costs have favourable effects. It implies that each unit increase or decrease in labour costs, raw material consumable costs, and inventory turnover costs will result in -1.34, -5.37, and 2.39 changes on return on assets. The relative importance of the independent variables' impact on return on assets was ascertained using the P-value found in the coefficient table. The model's labour costs, raw material consumable costs, and inventory turnover costs have negligible contributions because the p-value of 0.49 is higher than the alpha value of 0.05. Hence, we accept the null hypothesis which asserts that labour costs, raw material consumable costs and inventory turnover costs have no substantial impact on returns on assets of oil and gas companies in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The present research aims to assess Nigerian oil and gas companies' financial performance and backflush accounting from 2013 to 2022. The research methodology used in this study was ex-post factor. The study examined the yearly reports of Total Nigeria Plc that were released on the Nigerian Exchange Group floor after Nigeria embraced the International Financial Reporting Standards. Return on assets was one of the financial ratios evaluated in the investigation. Labour costs (wages and salaries), costs for raw materials and consumables (materials),

and costs associated with inventory turnover served as proxies for back-flush accounting. Using e-view 10 software, basic linear regression analyses were performed. The researchers draw the following conclusions in light of the analysis and findings of this study: labour costs (wages and salaries), raw material and consumable costs (material costs), and inventory turnover costs have no appreciable bearing on the returns on assets of Nigerian oil and gas businesses.

Recommendations

Following the conclusion and the results of the investigation, the following recommendations were put forward:

- i. Oil and gas companies in Nigeria should adopt backflush costing instead of traditional based costing for the sake of strategic management accounting. Decisions involving such changes might involve organisational staff members or their representatives, and staff members could be given incentives to support the change. One might employ all of these tactics to handle opposition to these modifications.
- ii. Since raw material consumable costs have a negative and insignificant influence on return on assets (ROA), the industry should endeavour to adopt and embrace the backflush accounting concept, which has enormous benefits in inventory control and irrelevant cost reduction in an advanced manufacturing environment.
- iii. Oil and gas companies particularly Total Nigeria Plc, should raise their level of profitability by using costing procedures that are most appropriate for their industrial environment, as inventory turnover costs have a positive but negligible effect on return on assets. The implementation of backflush accounting techniques needs to be improved in order to increase their capacity for innovation, remove unnecessary costs from operations, lower the cost of inventories, and provide flexibility for ongoing change and improved financial performance.

Limitations of the study

This study's scope is restricted to assessing Nigerian oil and gas companies' financial performance and backflush accounting. The data used in this study is restricted to information from Total Nigeria Plc, a particular company. The period of time is ten years, from 2013 to 2022. Given that the study only

examined one oil and gas company, the results cannot be applied to the entire oil and gas sector.

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Appendix

Year (s)	Profit After Tax 1	Total Assets 2	Return on assets (ROA) 3=1÷2	Inventory turnover cost (ITC) 4	Raw material consumable (RMC) 5=1÷2	Staff Cost (SCO) 6
2013	5,334,091	79,403,587	0.067176953	14,640,893	2,120,183	5,874,741
2014	4,423,733	95,512,428	0.046315784	19,826,763	1,740,789	6,906,511
2015	4,047,051	83,653,555	0.048378709	17,391,520	1,270,706	6,786,096
2016	14,797,095	136,928,160	0.10806466	34,902,844	464,342	7,483,750
2017	8,019,298	107,981,873	0.074265224	26,666,240	310,154	8,240,675
2018	7,960,893	132,520,783	0.060072789	30,045,177	4,512,056	8,815,810
2019	2,278,979	136,030,878	0.016753395	33,642,490	8,170,792	8,805,779
2020	2,063,385	143,612,885	0.014367687	21,619,936	4,318,892	8,612,443
2021	16,862,130	208,728,966	0.080784811	29,202,091	5,832,179	11,063,187
2022	16,118,376	307,815,723	0.052363719	59,275,749	23,090,221	13,076,549

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